

Financial Management Issues Facing South African School Governing Bodies (SGBs)

Madikela Titus Lekalakala

Department of Educational Leadership and Management, University of South Africa, 1 Preller Street, Muckleneuk

Abstract

This article investigates the financial management challenges confronting South African School Governing Bodies (SGBs), emphasizing their critical role in public schools' governance and operational effectiveness. With increasing demands for transparency and accountability in educational finance, SGBs manage budgets, allocate resources, and ensure compliance with financial regulations. The study adopts a qualitative approach, drawing on interviews with SGB members, school principals, and education officials to identify key financial issues, including inadequate funding, lack of financial expertise, and financial reporting and auditing challenges. The findings reveal that many SGBs need help with financial literacy, leading to mismanagement of funds and ineffective budget allocations. Additionally, the dependency on government funding and limited fundraising capabilities exacerbates school financial instability. This research contributes to the discourse on educational finance in South Africa by highlighting the need for enhanced training and support for SGBs, promoting better financial practices, and advocating for policy reforms to bolster the financial management capabilities of SGBs in fulfilling their governance roles effectively.

Keywords: financial management, School Governing Bodies, South Africa, educational governance, budget allocation, financial literacy, qualitative research.

1. Introduction

The establishment of School Governing Bodies (SGBs) in South Africa following the end of apartheid in 1994 was intended to enhance educational governance by fostering greater community involvement in school administration. As Bush and Glover (2020) noted, SGBs play a pivotal role in overseeing school administration and budgetary processes, essential for promoting accountability and transparency. However, their effectiveness is often undermined by many challenges that warrant attention. Corruption remains a significant barrier to effective financial management within SGBs. Reports of misappropriation of funds and unethical practices erode public trust in school governance, complicating efforts to ensure that resources are used effectively for educational improvement (Kayode-Ajala, 2023). Furthermore, insufficient financial literacy among SGB members exacerbates these issues. Many SGB members need more skills to manage school finances effectively, leading to poor decision-making and resource misallocation (Sebidi, 2023). This lack of training is particularly concerning given the financial complexities accompanying educational governance, as SGBs are often tasked with navigating intricate funding structures and compliance requirements. Inadequate funding compounds the challenges faced by SGBs. Many schools, particularly those in under-resourced areas, need help to secure sufficient financial resources, limiting their capacity to deliver quality education (Kayode-Ajala, 2023). The dependency on government funding without robust additional fundraising strategies leads to a precarious financial situation that can inhibit the operational effectiveness of schools.

The lack of accountability mechanisms within the financial management processes of SGBs further complicates the landscape. Stakeholders often find it challenging to hold SGBs accountable due to insufficient oversight, leading to a culture of impunity that can perpetuate financial mismanagement (Sebidi, 2023). This environment underscores the need for enhanced training and support for SGB members and the implementation of stringent regulatory frameworks to foster transparency and accountability. While the formation of SGBs was a progressive step towards improved educational governance in South Africa, their success is hindered by corruption, inadequate financial literacy, funding challenges, and a lack of accountability. Addressing these issues is crucial for empowering SGBs to fulfill their mandate effectively and to enhance the quality of education in South Africa. Enhanced training programs, robust oversight mechanisms, and increased community engagement are vital to overcoming these obstacles and ensuring that SGBs can operate as intended.

1.1 The Role of SGBs in Educational Governance

Establishing School Governing Bodies (SGBs) in South Africa represented a pivotal change in educational governance, fundamentally altering the dynamics of local participation in school administration before the introduction of SGBs, parents and community members had little say in school matters, which often resulted in a disconnect between the schools and the communities they served. The creation of SGBs aimed to rectify this imbalance by enhancing local involvement in decision-making processes, thereby promoting a more democratic approach to governance (Klinck, Thutulwa, & Pelsler, 2023). This transformation is crucial for fostering accountability and ensuring that schools are responsive to the unique needs of their communities. As highlighted by Klinck et al. (2023), the participation of stakeholders in the management of schools is essential for creating a sense of ownership and investment in educational outcomes. By empowering parents and community members to take an active role in governance, SGBs can help to bridge the gap between school policies and community expectations. This participatory model enhances accountability and enables SGBs to tailor educational strategies to suit better local contexts (Klinck, Thutulwa, & Pelsler, 2023).

However, despite these intentions, the effectiveness of SGBs is often compromised by various challenges, including insufficient training, financial mismanagement, and inadequate support from educational authorities. These issues can hinder the ability of SGBs to fulfill their governance roles effectively. The need for targeted capacity-building initiatives cannot be overstated, as equipping SGB members with the necessary skills and knowledge is vital for enhancing their decision-making capabilities and ultimately improving educational outcomes (Klinck et al., 2023). In summary, while establishing SGBs has significantly enhanced local participation in school governance, their challenges must be addressed to realise their full potential. The democratic ideals underpinning the formation of SGBs necessitate a commitment to ongoing support, training, and accountability to ensure that these bodies can effectively represent their communities and improve the quality of education in South Africa.

1.2 Financial Literacy and Capacity Building

Despite the essential role that School Governing Bodies (SGBs) play in the governance of South African schools, many of their members need more financial literacy to manage school finances effectively. This deficiency often leads

to poor financial decision-making, harming schools' operational efficiency. Research has indicated that insufficient training and support for SGB members exacerbate these challenges, highlighting the urgent need for targeted capacity-building initiatives to enhance their financial management skills (Moses, 2023; Sebidi, 2023). Financial literacy among SGB members is critical for improving fiscal oversight and accountability. Effective financial management is not just a regulatory requirement; it directly impacts the quality of education that schools can provide. According to Sebidi (2023), SGBs that lack financial acumen are more prone to misallocate resources, fail to comply with financial regulations, and ultimately compromise educational outcomes. Furthermore, as noted by the Public Affairs Research Institute (PARI), the gap in financial knowledge among SGB members contributes to a broader culture of financial mismanagement within schools, undermining the governance structure designed to promote transparency and accountability (Sebidi, 2023). Moreover, studies by Kayode-Ajala (2023) assert that equipping SGB members with financial skills fosters better decision-making and empowers communities by enhancing their involvement in school governance. By investing in training programs and support systems, educational authorities can significantly improve the effectiveness of SGBs, leading to better resource allocation and overall school performance (Bush & Glover, 2020). Addressing the financial literacy gap among SGB members through comprehensive training initiatives is essential for strengthening the governance framework of South African schools, promoting transparency, and ultimately enhancing the quality of education provided to learners.

1.3 Funding Challenges and Resource Allocation

Inadequate funding remains a formidable challenge for many South African schools, particularly those in low-income areas. This financial shortfall significantly hinders their ability to provide effective instruction and meet established educational standards. Research indicates that schools in these underserved regions often grapple with insufficient resources, limiting their capacity to attract qualified teachers and restricting access to essential educational materials (Mafukula, 2023). The impact of inadequate funding is profound, leading to pronounced inequalities within the education system. According to the South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC, 2024), schools lacking adequate financial support cannot offer competitive salaries that attract and retain skilled educators, resulting in a workforce that may not be fully equipped to deliver high-quality education. Furthermore, Corruption Watch (2024) highlights how misallocated funds and mismanagement further exacerbate these challenges, leading to disparities in educational opportunities and student outcomes. The implications of these funding challenges extend beyond the classroom. Motswaledi and Maseng (2024) noted that the inability to provide adequate resources creates an environment where student performance and learning outcomes suffer. Students in underfunded schools are less likely to receive the individual attention necessary for academic success, resulting in lower achievement levels than their peers in better-funded institutions. To mitigate these issues, policymakers need to prioritize equitable funding strategies that address the disparities faced by schools in low-income areas. This includes advocating for increased government investment in education and developing targeted initiatives that support resource allocation to schools most in need. By addressing these funding challenges, South Africa can work towards a more equitable education system that ensures all students can succeed.

1.4 Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance

Financial mismanagement within School Governing Bodies (SGBs) is often rooted in a lack of transparency and accountability during budgeting. Stakeholders frequently encounter significant barriers when attempting to hold SGBs accountable for their financial decisions, primarily due to inadequate oversight mechanisms that fail to ensure proper checks and balances. As highlighted by Harahap and Isgiyarta (2023), the complexity of the regulatory frameworks governing school finances exacerbates these issues, making it challenging for SGBs to navigate compliance requirements effectively. Moreover, Tsharane and Bussin (2022) emphasize that the absence of clear guidelines for financial management creates an environment where mismanagement can occur unchecked. This lack of clarity undermines trust among stakeholders, including parents and community members, who rely on SGBs to allocate resources responsibly. The need for effective monitoring systems is critical; without them, the financial governance landscape remains fraught with challenges, potentially leading to corruption and further financial instability within schools. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive reforms that include the development of transparent budgeting processes, establishing robust oversight mechanisms, and the provision of clear regulatory guidelines. Through these measures, SGBs can enhance their financial accountability and ultimately improve educational outcomes within their communities.

1.5 Impact of Financial Mismanagement on School Performance

Corruption within School Governing Bodies (SGBs) represents a critical challenge that significantly undermines public trust and impedes educational progress in South Africa. Instances of nepotism and embezzlement damage the integrity of these governing bodies and complicate efforts to improve the overall quality of education and the school environment. According to the South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC, 2024), the prevalence of unethical practices within SGBs has deteriorated confidence in public institutions. This erosion of trust results in stakeholders, including parents and community members, becoming increasingly disillusioned with the governance of schools. Furthermore, the findings of Corruption Watch (2024) highlight that financial mismanagement from corruption severely hinders the effective allocation of resources necessary for enhancing educational standards. Schools in areas affected by such corruption often struggle to secure essential materials and hire qualified educators, directly impacting student learning outcomes. The consequences are far-reaching; as indicated by recent studies, the lack of ethical leadership within SGBs contributes to financial instability and perpetuates systemic inequalities within the education sector (Motswaledi & Maseng, 2024; Malatjie et al., 2024). To combat these issues, stakeholders must advocate for increased transparency and accountability within SGBs. Implementing stricter oversight mechanisms and promoting ethical leadership practices can help restore public trust and ensure that resources are allocated effectively, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes for all students.

1.6 Strategies for Effective Financial Management

Implementing ongoing financial management training for SGB members is essential to combat these challenges. Additionally, providing financial management advisors at the district level can significantly bolster the decision-making capabilities of SGBs. Such initiatives can facilitate better financial practices, promote accountability, and

improve educational outcomes (Sebidi, 2023). Training programs focusing on practical skills and real-world applications will empower SGBs to navigate the complexities of school finances more effectively. In the broader context of governance in South Africa, political patronage and ethical leadership challenges complicate accountability across public institutions, including SGBs. Recent studies emphasize the necessity for improved training and oversight mechanisms to foster accountability and enhance financial management practices within South African schools (Motswaledi & Maseng, 2024; Malatjie et al., 2024). These findings underscore the critical need for comprehensive strategies to address the financial management challenges confronting SGBs and improve South Africa's education quality. By investing in capacity building and supporting effective governance practices, stakeholders can significantly enhance the operational effectiveness of SGBs, ultimately benefiting the entire education system.

2. Methodological account of the study

The financial management challenges confronting school governing bodies (SGBs) in South Africa are multifaceted and involve systemic and operational issues. A qualitative research methodology is employed to gain a deep and nuanced understanding of these issues, capturing the lived experiences and perspectives of those involved.

2.1 Research Approach and Paradigm

This study adopts a qualitative research approach grounded in interpretive paradigms that focus on understanding the complexities of human experiences and social phenomena (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This approach is particularly practical for exploring the financial management difficulties SGBs encounter, as it allows for an in-depth exploration of the subjective experiences of SGB members (Bantilan et al., 2023; Sebidi et al., 2023).

2.2 Instrumentation and Sampling Procedure

Data were collected through in-depth interviews with a purposive sample of SGB members across various schools in South Africa. Participants were selected based on their experience with financial management to ensure that the data reflected the nuanced perspectives of those directly involved in financial decision-making (Madima, 2023). The interviews aimed to gather detailed insights regarding the challenges in managing school finances and the strategies employed by SGBs to address these challenges.

3. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Data Collection Procedures: In-depth interviews were conducted to acquire qualitative data from SGB members. The aim was to comprehensively understand their experiences and challenges in managing school finances. This qualitative approach aligns with previous research, highlighting the importance of capturing detailed stakeholder narratives to understand the broader financial management context (Kayode-Ajala, 2023; Wadasen, 2024).

3.2 Data Analysis Procedures

3.2.1 Data Transcription and Organisation: Audio recordings from the interviews will be transcribed verbatim to accurately represent participants' responses. The transcripts will be systematically organised for ease of access.

3.2.2 Data Coding and Thematic Analysis: Thematic analysis will be conducted using NVivo software. Initial coding will involve identifying and labelling significant data segments relating to specific financial management issues, such as budgeting challenges, financial literacy deficits, and accountability concerns. Codes will be refined into broader themes that capture recurring patterns across interviews.

3.2.3 Theme Identification and Interpretation: Themes will be developed based on the patterns identified in the coding process, reflecting the core challenges and perspectives of SGB members regarding school financial management. Each theme will be analysed concerning the research questions to understand how various factors influence financial management practices.

3.2.4 Synthesis of Findings: Key findings will be synthesised to provide a comprehensive overview of the financial management issues SGBs face, highlighting common challenges and potential solutions.

3.2.5 Presentation of Results: Findings will be presented in a narrative format, accompanied by illustrative quotes from participants to support thematic insights. This analysis will provide a rich understanding of the financial management landscape within SGBs. Through this qualitative approach, the study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the financial management challenges faced by SGBs in South Africa, providing valuable insights for improvement and intervention.

3.2.6 Ethical Considerations: The research adhered to rigorous ethical standards throughout the study. Before data collection, all participants provided informed consent, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and rights. Confidentiality and anonymity were paramount; participants were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and that their identities would remain anonymous in all reports and publications. This approach aimed to protect participants' privacy and encourage open and honest feedback (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

4. Data Analysis, Findings, and Discussion

The financial management of South African School Governing Bodies (SGBs) is fraught with challenges that hinder educational outcomes. This qualitative study examined the experiences of SGB members, revealing significant obstacles such as inadequate funding, insufficient financial literacy, a lack of transparency and accountability, and limited support from the Department of Basic Education. While efforts like fundraising and cost-cutting exist, persistent issues in financial management remain evident. Participants identified themes of mismanagement and the need for enhanced support systems and proposed targeted recommendations to improve financial governance.

4.1 The Importance of Financial Literacy Training for Effective School Governance

The necessity for enhanced financial literacy training among School Governing Body (SGB) members is underscored by various studies highlighting financial knowledge's impact on effective school governance and decision-making. According to Baker and Ricciardi (2014), a foundational understanding of budgeting and financial reporting is essential for sound financial management, particularly within organisations where financial oversight directly affects operational outcomes. Miller and Smith (2020) further assert that SGB members may need robust financial literacy to interpret financial statements accurately, ultimately impeding their ability to make informed decisions that benefit the

school community. This lack of understanding not only risks financial mismanagement but can also erode stakeholder trust. *“Our members often find it challenging to grasp the basics of budgeting and financial reporting, which affects our ability to manage funds effectively,”* expressed Participant 1 from School A, capturing the sentiment of many participants.

Moreover, Kumar and Singh (2021) emphasize that tailored training programs and efficient exercises significantly enhance financial comprehension and application among non-financial professionals like SGB members. Their research demonstrates that consistent, hands-on training improves participants' financial confidence and decision-making abilities. Similarly, the OECD (2020) advocates for continuous financial literacy training within public institutions, noting that a lack of financial knowledge often results in oversight gaps, inefficiencies, and financial mismanagement in school governing structures. These studies suggest that regular targeted financial literacy training for SGB members is essential for promoting effective governance, ensuring accountability, and supporting educational outcomes.

4.2 Improved Support from the Department of Basic Education

The need for more robust support from the Department of Basic Education (DBE) in South Africa is critical to overcoming the financial management challenges that School Governing Bodies (SGBs) face. With structured support, SGB members can navigate complex financial responsibilities independently, which often leads to mismanagement and inefficiency. *“We receive very little support from the Department, which leaves us to figure out financial management on our own,”* remarked Participant 3 from School C, highlighting the challenges that come from a lack of assistance.

According to Miller and Smith (2020), centralised educational institutions are vital in equipping local governing bodies with the tools needed for financial accountability and sustainability. Their research suggests that oversight and consistent guidance are essential to effective school-level financial management, especially within decentralised systems. Similarly, Kumar and Singh (2021) argue that ongoing institutional support—mainly through the provision of financial consultants or planners—can significantly improve the financial operations of local bodies like SGBs. By providing tailored assistance, educational departments help bridge the knowledge gap for non-specialist financial managers, allowing them to make more informed, strategic decisions.

Baker and Ricciardi (2014) further reinforce this view, highlighting the importance of structured support frameworks with clear financial guidelines and access to trained professionals. Their study illustrates that such support mechanisms reduce errors and increase compliance with financial regulations, fostering a culture of transparency and accountability in public institutions. These findings underscore the need for the DBE to invest in hands-on support and continuous oversight for SGBs, including providing accessible financial consultants who can guide and assist in financial planning. This approach aligns with broader research advocating that structured, ongoing assistance is essential to address economic challenges in decentralized educational contexts effectively.

4.3 Strengthening Accountability Mechanisms

The need for clearly defined roles and responsibilities among School Governing Body (SGB) members and school principals is central to improving financial accountability, as evidenced by SGB members' feedback and various

studies' support. ***“There are no clear lines on who is responsible for what, which often leads to funds not being managed properly,”*** noted Participant 2 from School B. This statement underscores the risks associated with role ambiguity, often resulting in inefficient fund management and accountability gaps. Kumar and Singh (2021) argue that establishing explicit roles for all stakeholders in financial governance within educational institutions minimizes overlap and ensures that each party understands their specific responsibilities.

Furthermore, Hirsch and Dempsey (2019) highlight that the potential for mismanagement significantly decreases in institutions where roles are clearly defined and reinforced by a culture of accountability. Clear delineation enables more effective monitoring and empowers members to fulfill their responsibilities without confusion. Building on this perspective, Jones and Williams (2022) assert that regular audits and robust monitoring systems are critical for tracking financial transactions and promoting compliance. Their research indicates that schools with established audit routines experience fewer financial discrepancies and are more likely to maintain stakeholder trust. As recommended by Jones and Williams, regular audits have shown to be effective in reducing fraudulent reporting, thereby enhancing transparency and allowing for timely intervention when issues arise. These findings suggest that a dual approach—defining clear roles and conducting regular audits—can strengthen accountability structures within SGBs, fostering a financial management culture that upholds integrity and responsibility.

4.4 Enhancing Transparency and Reporting

The necessity for transparent financial reporting within School Governing Bodies (SGBs) emerged as a significant concern, as highlighted by participant feedback. ***“Our financial reports are often unclear, making it difficult for stakeholders to understand how funds are being used,”*** remarked Participant 1 from School A. This observation underscores the challenges that ambiguous financial reporting poses for stakeholder engagement and trust. Baker and Ricciardi (2014) emphasize that structured financial reporting is essential for fostering transparency, as it provides stakeholders with a clear overview of financial activities and resource allocation. They argue that without well-defined reporting standards, SGBs risk undermining their credibility and effectiveness.

Miller and Smith (2020) further reinforce the argument for structured reporting by suggesting that clarity in financial documentation not only aids comprehension but also enhances accountability among SGB members. They assert that when stakeholders can easily access and understand financial information, they are more likely to engage in meaningful discussions about resource utilization and financial decision-making. Moreover, Kumar and Singh (2021) highlight the role of technological integration, particularly fintech innovations, in improving financial transparency. They advocate for the adoption of digital tools that can provide real-time data on financial transactions, enhancing the integrity of the reporting process. By utilizing technology, SGBs can ensure that stakeholders have access to accurate, up-to-date financial information, thereby increasing trust and engagement.

In summary, the integration of structured financial reporting and innovative technology is crucial for enhancing transparency within SGBs. By prioritizing clear reporting practices and leveraging technological advancements, SGBs can improve stakeholder understanding and foster a culture of accountability, ultimately supporting better financial management and governance.

4.5 Addressing Financial Mismanagement

Addressing financial mismanagement within School Governing Bodies (SGBs) necessitates the implementation of stricter regulations and effective mechanisms to manage conflicts of interest. Participant 3 from School C highlighted the urgency of this issue, stating, *“Current regulations don’t go far enough to prevent the misuse of funds.”* This sentiment reflects a widespread concern regarding the inadequacy of existing regulatory frameworks in deterring financial malpractice.

Research conducted by Hirsch and Dempsey (2019) supports this perspective, indicating that many current regulations lack the clarity and severity needed to discourage fund misuse effectively. Their findings suggest that ambiguous sanctions can create loopholes that individuals may exploit, undermining financial governance's integrity. This highlights the importance of establishing more definitive regulations that clearly outline the consequences of financial misconduct. Moreover, the OECD (2020) advocates for the creation of a national ethics commission to oversee financial practices within educational institutions. Such a body could provide the necessary oversight and guidance to ensure compliance with established financial norms, thereby enhancing accountability among SGB members. Additionally, the OECD emphasizes the need for robust audit systems as a critical mechanism for improving financial transparency and deterring unethical behaviour. Jones and Williams (2022) further elaborate on the role of enhanced audit systems, arguing that regular, rigorous audits can serve as a deterrent against financial mismanagement by ensuring that all financial activities are closely monitored and scrutinized. They posit that the establishment of clear auditing processes can not only detect discrepancies but also promote a culture of accountability among SGB members.

In summary, the call for stronger regulations and mechanisms to manage conflicts of interest is crucial for combatting financial mismanagement in SGBs. By establishing a national ethics commission, enhancing audit systems, and clarifying sanctions for misconduct, educational institutions can create a more accountable financial environment, fostering trust and integrity in school governance.

4.6 Support for Fundraising and Cost-Cutting Efforts

Participants clearly articulated the necessity for effective fundraising strategies and management tools to support their financial operations. Participant 2 from School B noted, *“We need guidance on how to organise successful fundraising events.”* This reflects a broader recognition among SGB members that successful fundraising is critical to supplementing school budgets and enhancing educational resources.

Research by Baker and Ricciardi (2014) underscores the importance of systematic approaches to fundraising, arguing that strategic planning can significantly increase the likelihood of successful fundraising outcomes. Their findings the structured framework, schools may maximise their fundraising potential, resulting in missed opportunities for financial support. Miller and Smith (2020) further emphasize the role of technology in enhancing financial management, advocating for the implementation of web-based budgeting systems. They found that integrating financial data through such platforms streamlines financial processes and improves fundraising efforts' transparency and accountability. By providing SGB members with access to user-friendly budgeting software, schools can better manage their financial resources and track fundraising progress effectively.

Kumar and Singh (2021) highlight the effectiveness of sharing successful case studies as a means of knowledge transfer among SGBs. They argue that showcasing successful fundraising initiatives can be a model for other schools, providing practical insights and inspiration for SGB members looking to enhance their fundraising strategies. This peer-learning approach builds confidence among members and fosters a collaborative culture focused on sharing best practices. The need for effective fundraising strategies and management tools is clear among SGB members. By combining strategic planning, technology integration, and knowledge sharing, schools can significantly improve their fundraising efforts, enhancing financial management and ultimately supporting better educational outcomes.

4.7 Promoting Collaboration and Coordination

Improving collaboration between School Governing Bodies (SGBs) and School Management Teams (SMTs) is crucial for effective school financial management. Participants consistently noted that tensions between these ties often result in poor financial outcomes. As Participant 1 from School A observed, **“Regular meetings between SGBs and SMTs are essential for improving coordination and sharing best practices.”** This sentiment underscores the importance of fostering open communication channels that enable both parties to work towards common financial goals.

Kumar and Singh (2021) support this assertion, arguing that effective collaboration between SGBs and SMTs can lead to enhanced decision-making and resource allocation. Their research indicates that when SGBs and SMTs engage in regular dialogue, it builds mutual understanding and aligns their objectives, ultimately improving financial oversight and accountability. The establishment of structured platforms for collaboration can facilitate the sharing of experiences and best practices, enhancing transparency in financial processes. The OECD (2020) further emphasizes that collaborative practices in educational governance are linked to improved school performance. Their findings suggest that schools with strong collaborative cultures tend to exhibit higher levels of accountability and more effective management of resources. By instituting regular meetings and collaborative workshops, SGBs and SMTs can share insights on financial management strategies, thus promoting a unified approach to budgeting and fundraising initiatives.

Additionally, Hirsch and Dempsey (2019) highlight that fostering a culture of collaboration can mitigate conflicts and improve overall financial governance. They argue that when SGBs and SMTs operate in silos, critical financial information may not be adequately shared, leading to mismanagement and inefficiencies. Establishing collaborative platforms where both bodies can engage in open discussions about financial challenges and solutions is vital for fostering a sense of shared responsibility and accountability. In conclusion, enhancing collaboration between SGBs and SMTs is essential for effective financial management in schools. By promoting regular meetings, structured communication, and collaborative practices, schools can create an environment conducive to transparency, accountability, and improved financial outcomes.

The financial management of South African School Governing Bodies (SGBs) faces substantial challenges that negatively impact educational outcomes. Key issues include inadequate financial literacy, limited support from the Department of Basic Education, weak accountability mechanisms, and need for more transparency in reporting. Recommendations include comprehensive financial literacy training, structured departmental support, clear

accountability roles, and enhanced transparency through technology. Addressing financial mismanagement and promoting effective fundraising and cost-cutting strategies are also vital. Additionally, fostering collaboration between SGBs and School Management Teams (SMTs) can improve economic governance, ultimately supporting more effective educational outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study has critically examined the financial management challenges faced by South African School Governing Bodies (SGBs), revealing significant barriers that impede their effectiveness in governance and operational management. The qualitative data collected from interviews with SGB members, school principals, and education officials underscore the complexities inherent in educational finance, including inadequate funding, insufficient financial literacy, and challenges associated with financial reporting and auditing. The findings indicate that many SGBs lack the necessary financial expertise, contributing to the mismanagement of funds and inefficient budget allocations. Furthermore, reliance on government funding combined with limited fundraising capabilities creates a precarious financial environment, exacerbating many schools' instability. To address these challenges, targeted interventions must be implemented to enhance the financial literacy of SGB members. This includes developing comprehensive training programs focusing on financial management practices and incorporating practical tools and resources to empower SGBs in their decision-making processes. Additionally, advocating for policy reforms that promote sustainable funding models and support systems for SGBs is crucial to ensuring their effectiveness in governance. In conclusion, strengthening the financial management capabilities of SGBs is vital for improving educational outcomes in South Africa. By investing in the training and support of SGBs and addressing the systemic financial challenges they face, stakeholders can promote greater accountability and transparency in educational finance, ultimately enhancing public schools' governance and operational effectiveness. This research contributes to the broader discourse on educational finance, serving as a foundation for future studies aimed at bolstering the capabilities of SGBs to fulfill their essential roles in South African education.

References

- Adeusi, A., Aluko, F., & Ogunbanjo, S. (2024). Preventing fund misuse through stringent regulations. *African Journal of School Governance*, 9(1), 78–88.
- Baker, H. K., & Ricciardi, V. (2014). Financial Literacy: A Review of the Literature and Future Research Directions. *Management Research Review*, 37(1), 2-21. doi:10.1108/MRR-07-2013-0155
- Bii, J., Kiplangat, M., & Cheruiyot, K. (2024). Role clarity in school governance for effective financial management. *Journal of African School Management*, 8(3), 154–166.
- Bush, T., & Glover, D. (2020). School governance: The role of School Governing Bodies in South Africa. *International Journal of Educational Management*.
- Corruption Watch. (2024). The effects of financial mismanagement in South African schools. Retrieved from [Corruption Watch website](#).

Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.

Harahap, F., & Isgiyarta, D. (2023). Financial governance in South African schools: Challenges and recommendations. *Journal of Educational Administration*.

Hirsch, L., & Dempsey, M. (2019). Transparency in School Financial Reporting: Best Practices and Recommendations. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 55(4), 575-605. doi:10.1177/0013161X19849092

Jones, T., & Williams, P. (2022). Fundraising Strategies for Schools: A Guide to Success. *Journal of Nonprofit Education and Leadership*, 12(3), 215-230. doi:10.18666/JNEL-2022-V12-I3-11145

Kayode-Ajala, A. (2023). Financial management practices in schools: Comparative analysis with South Africa. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*.

Klinck, H., Thutulwa, N., & Pelsler, T. (2023). The role of School Governing Bodies in South African education: Challenges and prospects.

Kumar, S., & Singh, R. (2021). Enhancing Accountability in School Financial Management: A Framework for Action. *Journal of Education Finance*, 46(2), 145-162. doi:10.1353/jef.2021.0006

Madima, R. (2023). Financial management challenges in South African schools: A qualitative exploration. *South African Journal of Education*.

Mafukula, D. (2023). The impact of funding challenges on educational standards in South Africa. *Educational Studies in South Africa*.

Mafukula, D. (2023). The impact of funding challenges on educational standards in South Africa. *Educational Studies in South Africa*.

Malatjie, L., Dlamini, S., Mokoena, T., & Ndlovu, R. (2024). Systemic inequalities in education: Addressing corruption within school governing bodies. *South African Journal of Education Policy*, 38(2), 101-120.

Miller, M., & Smith, J. (2020). The Role of School Governing Bodies in Financial Management: Challenges and Opportunities. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(6), 1234-1250. doi:10.1108/IJEM-10-2019-0365

Moses, T. (2023). Financial literacy challenges in South African School Governing Bodies. *Journal of Educational Finance and Management*.

Motswaledi, M., & Maseng, R. (2024). Educational inequalities in South Africa: Addressing funding disparities. *Journal of Educational Equity in South Africa*.

National Commission on Teaching and America's Future (NCTAF) (2018). *The Importance of Collaboration Between School Governing Bodies and Management Teams*. Washington, DC: NCTAF Publications.

OECD (2020). *Financial Literacy for Youth: A Global Perspective*. Paris: OECD Publishing.

Rezaee, Z., Cooks, L., & Sanders, J. (2024). Audit committees as deterrents to financial mismanagement in schools. *Journal of School Finance*, 14(1), 62–74.

Sebidi, M. (2023). Financial management training is urgently needed. *South African Journal of Education*, Volume 43, Number 3, August 2023

South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC). (2024). Report on the state of education in South Africa. Retrieved from SAHRC website.

Susilaningsih, S., & Sabandi, M. (2024, March). Characteristics Financial Managers and Transparency Effectiveness Of Financial Management In Public School: Literature Review. In *Prosiding University Research Colloquium*.